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Annotation: This article discusses interactive methods of teaching a foreign language at an early stage. In particular, the technology of using “brainstorming” is described in detail. Discussed Pros and Cons of this Method.

Brainstorming is one of the popular techniques of participative approach to decision making which can be employed in a pedagogic situation as well. The brainstorming method is an operational method for solving a problem based on stimulating creative activity, in which discussion participants are invited to express as many possible solutions as possible, including the most fantastic ones. Then, from the total number of ideas expressed, the most successful ones that can be used in practice are selected. Brainstorming is a widely used way of producing new ideas for solving scientific and practical problems. Its purpose is the organization of collective mental activity in the search for innovative ways to solve problems. Using the brainstorming method in the educational process allows us to solve the following problems: students' creative assimilation of educational material; the relationship of theoretical knowledge with practice; activation of educational and cognitive activities of students; the formation of the ability to concentrate attention and mental efforts on solving an urgent problem; the formation of the experience of collective mental activity.

Brainstorming is a tool that uses a relaxed, informal atmosphere combined with lateral thinking to solve problems. In spite of its importance in the generation of new ideas, many students do not have enough training to use it. This activity will teach students to brainstorm effectively. It can be carried out in a one-period session. No materials are required apart from a pen or pencil and sheets of paper except in a sophisticated high tech classroom. The most important thing about brainstorming is that there should be no criticism of ideas. Students try to open up possibilities and discard wrong assumptions about the limits of the problem. Judgments and analysis of ideas are explored after the brainstorming process while focus should be at this stage on idea generation.

The major purpose of brainstorming as a teaching strategy is to foster and enhance communication skill, help to promote thinking and decision-making skill as well as foster different viewpoints and opinions. It may equally be used in all key areas of learning. However, the major limitation is that it is generally not suitable for younger levels because of the level of reasoning required in order for it to work. The teacher must equally be able to guide and give aid as necessary considering the class environment as such considerations often determine the outcomes. In brainstorming techniques, the instructor carefully plans the lesson to reach the desired learning outcomes. The group interacts in response to questions, and the instructor refrains from entering the discussion as an active participant. Students are encouraged to learn about the subject by actively sharing information, experiences, and opinions.

Advantages of brainstorming some of the advantages of brainstorming technique are summarized below:

- The target group can create a greater number of alternative responses since the group's information and knowledge tend to be more comprehensive and reliable.
- The group decision making is democratic in nature. The democratic processes are more easily acceptable and more consistent with the democratic principles which ensure equal academic opportunities.

-Implementation of a brainstorming based decision is more effective as the entire group participate. Advantages of brainstorming show how important it is. The relevance of the same can be felt both in general and educational context. However, it may be more relevant and feasible in educational institutional because educational administration is totally based on human relation and brainstorming is highly democratic in approach.

-Brainstorming brings new ideas on how to tackle a particular problem – the freethinking atmosphere encourages creativity, even imperfectly developed thoughts may push the thinking of other participants. -Problems are defined better as questions arise – alternatives appear in a new or different perspective and novel approaches to an issue can arise during the process.

-Brainstorming helps to reduce conflicts – it helps participants to see other points of view and possibly change their perspective on problems. All participants have equal status and an equal opportunity to participate. The findings show that brainstorming is a useful technique of teaching which catches attention of both the teachers and learners.

Disadvantages of brainstorming:

- Not everyone actively takes part in brainstorming. Some participants are more quiet and don't like to speak spontaneously in groups.
- Other participants speak too much.
- Some participants need longer to understand the theme and can't immediately provide ideas.
- It's not possible to cover all risks with brainstorming.
- The results of brainstorming are largely groupthink and not necessarily individual thoughts or ideas.

Conclusion: As a rule, brainstorming is very productive and gives good results besides brainstorming sessions can be a useful strategy to encourage genuine collaboration and interaction in the classroom. Putting together a well-stated

problem and careful planning strategies can lead to meaningful idea generation and idea building which can be used in solving problems or addressing specific course-related issues.

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